

Women's Literacy and Prenatal Caregiver Characteristics as Significant Determinants of Optimal Birth Preparedness Coverage among Antenatal Mothers Attending a Tertiary Care Hospital in North Chennai

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Received: 25-04-2024 / Revised: 23-05-2024 / Accepted: 26-06-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Introduction: Pregnancy and the birth of a child is a transformational phase in the life of the parents. Knowledge and awareness among antenatal women during this period are critical to reduce maternal and neonatal mortality. Birth Preparedness and Complication Readiness (BPACR) is the process for planning normal birth, and anticipating the actions needed in case of emergency.

Aim: This study was conducted in view of assessing the level of Birth Preparedness and Complication Readiness among antenatal women and to determine the factors associated with BPACR, which will be helpful in improving the ongoing maternal and child health programs.

Materials and Methods: This was a hospital based cross sectional study conducted in Government RSRM hospital, Chennai. The study subjects were antenatal mothers in second and third trimesters.

Results: Among 144 antenatal women, 49.31% of the study participants were found to have optimal BPACR practice. Women's education level showed a significant association with BPACR ($p=0.0000$). Women who had experienced complications in their previous pregnancies had increased BPACR ($p=0.0030$). Unsatisfactory BPACR practice among women was due to poor knowledge of key danger signs. There was a significant association between BPACR and women who were taken care of in their mother's house ($p=0.0060$).

Conclusion: Increasing Birth Preparedness and Complication Readiness (BPACR) awareness is very crucial among women with lower educational levels and those for whom prenatal care givers are not their mothers. Further, there is an unmet need for specific health literacy among all antenatal women about the key danger signs of pregnancy, delivery and postpartum.

Keywords: Birth Preparedness and Complication Readiness, Antenatal Women, Danger Signs of Pregnancy.

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Introduction

Maternal mortality still continues to be one of the gargantuan public health challenges in the country and educating women is equal to equipping them with the power to improving the lives around them. As per 2011 population census, the literacy rate in Tamil Nadu has seen an upward trend and female literacy is 73.14 percent. [1] According to Sample Registration System statistics 2018-20, the current Maternal Mortality Ratio (MMR) in India is 97 per lakh live births. [2] Most maternal deaths are related to obstetric complications such as hemorrhage, sepsis, abortion, hypertensive disorders, obstructed

labour and so on. Apart from these medical causes, certain socio-economic-cultural determinants like illiteracy, low socio-economic status and preference for home deliveries also contribute to these deaths.[3] The United Nations target for MMR under the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) is 70 per lakh live births, which is to be achieved by 2030[4] In India, a steady reduction in maternal deaths has been reported in the last two decades and the highest decline was from 2004-06, after the launch of National Rural Health Mission (NRHM) and its numerous initiatives [3]. Janani Suraksha

Yojana (JSY) is a 100% centrally sponsored scheme under NRHM, launched in 2005 and it has resulted in increased institutional deliveries. Another such initiative is Dr. Muthulakshmi Reddy Maternity Benefit Scheme (MRMBS), an exclusive scheme introduced by the state government of Tamil Nadu which provides a sum of Rs.18000 for the pregnant woman in five installments and ensures the health of both mother and infant. [5]

Even though such schemes are well implemented, and people are utilizing the monetary benefit, there is still certain lacunae in delivering full-fledged health services, which when properly addressed can pave the way for further reduction in maternal complications and deaths. The maternal mortality can be categorized by the three delays model into three aspects - delay in decision to access care, delay in reaching care and delay in receiving adequate and appropriate treatment. [6] Birth Preparedness and Complication Readiness (BPACR) is an important strategy that prevents these delays and encourages pregnant women to plan for births and deal with emergencies, if they occur.

BPACR is an approach which improves the use and effectiveness of maternal and newborn health services. BPACR is an intervention included by WHO as an essential element of antenatal care package. [7] Improving BPACR increases the knowledge of mothers about danger signs and eventually prevents the delays in seeking appropriate care. Hence our study was conducted to assess the status of BPACR among pregnant women and to study the various other factors associated with it.

Methodology

The study was a hospital based cross-sectional study conducted in a tertiary care hospital in North Chennai between May and June 2018 after getting approval from the Institutional Ethical Committee. Sample size was calculated based on the reported individual level BPACR index of 41% in a study from PHC in Delhi [8], India, with 95% Confidence Interval and relative precision of 20. The final sample size calculated was 144.

The study subjects were antenatal mothers in second and third trimesters. Those who were in the first trimester and whose expected date of delivery was just two weeks ahead and also pregnant women in active labour, mentally and physically incapable of interview and those not willing to participate were excluded from the study.

Informed written consent was taken from all the study participants after explaining the study protocol. A pretested semi structured questionnaire was used to collect information.

Data was collected by consecutive sampling method. The first 12 pregnant women who attended the antenatal OP and satisfied the inclusion and exclu-

sion criteria were included in the study each day for 12 days till we reached the final sample size.

The questionnaire included socio-demographic details, obstetric details, knowledge about key danger signs of pregnancy/delivery/postpartum and the five BPACR components⁹ which are as follows.

1. Awareness about more than 8 danger signs of pregnancy
2. Identified skilled birth attendant for delivery
3. Identified mode of transportation
4. Saved money to pay for expenses
5. Identified a compatible blood donor

Optimal BPACR practice was defined as following at least three out of the five key components of BPACR.

The literacy status of the study participant was categorized as high if she had finished high school and above; and low if she studied middle school and below. Modified Kuppusamy Scale (2018) was used to calculate the socio-economic status.

A minimum of 4 antenatal visits is considered ideal, i.e. 1st visit- within 12 weeks; 2nd visit- between 14 and 26 weeks; 3rd visit- between 28 and 34 weeks and 4th visit between 36 weeks and term. Women who received all the above four services viz., registration of pregnancy, Tetanus immunization, consumed Iron folic acid and underwent minimum antenatal visits were considered to have good antenatal care.

Data was entered in Microsoft excel and analyzed in IBM SPSS version 21. Descriptive statistics was used to describe the distribution of all variables. Analytical statistics like Chi Square tests was used to find the association between each independent variables & BPACR indicators; and Multivariate analysis was done amongst the significant variables.

Results

Majority of the study population were between 20-29 years (86.8%) and the mean age was 24.9 (± 3.9) years. Majority of them were literates and 104 (72.22%) had studied high school and above. More than three-fourths of them (88.19%) were from nuclear family and 78.47% lived in a pucca house. Most of our study population was Hindus 88.19%. Nearly, 65.28% of their husbands studied high school and above.

Nearly three-fourths (72.22%) of them belonged to socio-economic status 4 and above. About 67 (46.53%) were primi, 22 (15.28%) of study participants had previous abortions and 37 (25.69%) of them experienced obstetric complications during the previous delivery. More than half of the women 89 (61.81%) were taken care of in mother-in-law's house and about 70.14% (101) were the primary decision makers in the family. All of them were

registered and had Maternal and Child Protection (MCP) card except one person who was a migrant from other state. Almost all, 142 members (98.61%) had ideal number of antenatal visits. All of them received tetanus immunization. 139 (96.53%) members were consuming Iron and Folic Acid tablets regularly. The remaining 5 were also prescribed but they discontinued the tablet due to vomiting. Women who received all the above four

services (139, 96.53%) were considered to have good antenatal care. About 78.47% (113) of women were availing financial assistance provided by the government through JSY and MRMBBS schemes. Remaining 21.53% (31) were not availing due to various reasons such as lack of knowledge about the schemes, registration of pregnancy in private hospitals, maternal age less than 18 at the time of pregnancy.

Table 1: Awareness of danger signs during pregnancy, labour and puerperium

awareness of danger signs	n=144	Frequency (%)
During Pregnancy		
Vaginal bleeding	63	43.75
Abdominal pain	132	91.70
Swelling of face and hands	45	31.25
Reduced fetal movements	48	33.33
Vaginal discharge	29	20.14
Blurring of vision	6	4.17
Excessive vomiting	32	22.22
Fever more than 24 hours	38	26.39
Palpitation, easy fatiguability, breathlessness at rest	21	14.58
Headache	22	15.28
During Labour		
Severe vaginal bleeding	17	11.81
Prolonged labour	1	0.69
Convulsions	25	17.36
Retained placenta	4	2.78
During Puerperium		
Severe vaginal bleeding	25	17.36
Foul smelling vaginal discharge	1	0.69
High grade fever for first 7 days	59	40.97

The most common danger sign which the women were aware about was abdominal pain (91.67%), followed by vaginal bleeding (43.75%), and high-grade fever for more than 7 days (40.97%) [Table 1]. A woman who recalled at least 8 danger signs was considered to be aware about it. Only about 16 (11.11%) of them were aware about greater than 8 danger signs of pregnancy.

Components of BPACR: Majority 128 (88.89%) of them were unaware about the danger signs during pregnancy, labour and puerperium. About 138 (95.83%) identified a skilled birth attendant for their delivery. About 135 (93.75%) women had identified the mode of transportation in case of

emergency. Less than half of them 46 (31.9%) have saved money for expenses. Only 43 (29.9%) of them had identified a compatible blood donor in case of emergency.

A score of one was given for each of these components and those who scored three and above were considered to have optimal BPACR. 49.31% of women in our study were found to have optimal BPACR.

The source of knowledge about BPACR components was mainly provided by health workers 52.78% (76), followed by family members (45.83%). Remaining 1.39% of women claimed media to be their knowledge source.

Table 2: Association of BPACR with other variables

S.No	Study Variables	Optimal BPACR				Total	χ^2	p
		Yes (n=71)		No (n=73)				
		N	%	N	%			
1	Age (years)							
	≥25	31	46.97	35	53.03	66	0.266	0.606
	<25	40	51.28	38	48.72	78		
2	Religion							
	Hindu	62	48.82	65	51.18	127	0.1019	0.7495
	Non-Hindu	9	52.94	8	47.06	17		

3	Education							
	Middle school and below	8	20	32	80	40	19.0297	0.00001
	High school and above	63	60.58	41	39.42	104		
4	Family type							
	Nuclear	36	43.9	46	56.1	82	2.2244	0.1358
	Non-nuclear	35	56.45	27	43.55	62		
5	Type of house							
	Pucca	59	52.21	54	47.79	113	1.7744	0.1828
	Non-pucca	12	38.71	19	61.29	31		
6	Education of husband							
	Middle school and below	20	40	30	60	50	2.6536	0.1033
	High school and above	51	54.26	43	45.74	94		
7	Socio-economic status							
	Upper (1,2,3)	23	57.5	17	42.5	40	1.4879	0.2225
	Lower (4,5)	48	46.15	56	53.85	104		
8	Gravidity							
	Primi	29	43.28	38	56.72	67	1.8179	0.1775
	Non-primi	42	54.55	35	45.45	77		
9	Previous Abortion							
	Yes	14	63.64	8	36.36	22	2.1336	0.1441
	No	57	46.72	65	53.28	122		
10	Previous delivery type							
	Normal	23	53.49	20	46.51	43	0.0216	0.883
	LSCS	15	51.72	14	48.28	29		
11	Previous Obstetric complication							
	Yes	26	70.27	11	29.73	37	8.7559	0.003
	No	45	42.06	62	57.94	107		
12	Primary decision making							
	Dependent	20	46.51	23	53.49	43	0.1915	0.6617
	Independent	51	50.5	50	49.5	101		
13	Taken care of in							
	Mother's home	35	63.64	20	36.36	55	7.3117	0.006
	In law's home	36	40.45	53	59.55	89		
14	ANC services							
	Good	70	50.36	69	49.64	139	1.7798	0.1821
	Bad	1	20	4	80	5		

Table 2 shows association between BPACR and other study variables. Woman's education level showed a significant association with BPACR (p=0.0000) in our study. Women who had experienced complications such as anemia, gestational diabetes mellitus and pre-eclampsia in their previ-

ous pregnancies too had a significant association with BPACR (p=0.0030).

There was also a significant association between BPACR and women who were taken care of in their mother's house. (p=0.0060).

Table 3: Multivariate analysis of BPACR

S.No	Study Variables	Optimal BPACR				B	Sig	Exp(B)	95% C.I.
		Yes (n=71)		No (n=73)					
		N	%	N	%				
1.	Education								
	Middle school and below	8	20	32	80	2.212	0.000	9.135	3.2 – 26.08
	High school and above	63	60.58	41	39.42				
2.	Previous Obstetric complication								
	Yes	26	70.27	11	29.73	-1.911	0.000	0.148	0.053-0.41
	No	45	42.06	62	57.94				
3.	Taken care of in								
	Mother's home	35	63.64	20	36.36	-1.014	0.011	0.363	0.17-0.79
	In law's home	36	40.45	53	59.55				

Multivariate analysis between the three significant variables showed that education plays a very significant role of improving BPACR by almost 9.1 times. [Table 3]

Discussion

Nearly half, 49.31% of women were found to have optimal BPACR in our study. Its slightly higher than the other Indian studies conducted in Bangalore [7] (43.98%), Delhi [8] (41%), West Bengal [4] (43.9%). However, it was lower than that found in Dakshina Kannada district, Karnataka [9] (79.35%) and the study by Patil MS et.al [10] (55.83%) done in a rural area in Maharashtra. This could be due to the increase awareness of danger signs among their study participants. BPACR reported from different countries such as Ethiopia [11] (17%), Ghana [12] (14.7%) is less when compared to our study, which can be attributed to higher female literacy, increased utility of antenatal services and higher proportion of institutional deliveries in our state.

In our study, only 11.11% were aware about at least eight danger signs during pregnancy, labour and puerperium. Similarly lower levels of awareness were documented by the studies done by Patil MS et.al [10] and Mukhopadhyay D et al [3]; whereas the study done by Aksaya KM et al [9] had higher awareness about danger signs (53.8%), hence increasing the optimal BPACR. Thus, imparting focused knowledge about key danger signs and reinforcing the red flag signs are of high importance. Healthcare workers should be encouraged to educate the pregnant mother and her family members about the danger signs to reduce pregnancy related complications thereby reducing maternal morbidity and mortality.

Majority of the study participants (95.83%) have identified skilled birth attendant for delivery, which is similar to the studies done by Aksaya KM et al [9] and Patil MS et.al [10]. In our study 93.75% women have identified the mode of transport which is considerably higher than the studies done in West Bengal [3] (27.3%), Karnataka [9] (71.7%) and Maharashtra [10] (72.25%). This could be due to easy accessibility of transport, as our study was done in an urban area coupled with high literacy rates among the present study population.

Only 31.9% of the women in this study have saved money for delivery and its expenses, which is similar to other studies [3,10]. In our study, only 29.86% antenatal women had identified a compatible blood donor, which is similar to the study done by Patil MS et.al [10] but marginally higher than the studies done elsewhere by Mukhopadhyay D et al [3] (9.6%) and Aksaya KM et al [9] (15.8%) have documented. Anemia and post-partum hemorrhage being the most important causes of maternal mortality in India, [13], this finding further reiter-

ates the utmost need for encouraging and assisting antenatal women to pre-identify a compatible blood donor. Women's literacy level showed a positive association with BPACR ($p=0.0000$) which is echoed in numerous studies. Hence focused BCC activities should concentrate on pregnant women with lower educational levels to increase their BPACR levels. Women who had experienced complications such as anemia, GDM, pre-eclampsia in their previous pregnancies had a significant association with BPACR ($p=0.0030$). This could be attributed to their increased knowledge about the danger signs.

There was a significant association between BPACR and women who were taken care of in their mother's house ($p=0.0060$). Studies have shown that mothers, however, had a better health status when they had a strong support system of social networks. Researches abound on the necessity for birth environment. [14] This is in congruence with the cultural practices of Tamil Nadu as well as Indian traditions, at large, to go to mother's place for first delivery. If she is unable to do so the mother will usually come and live with her during this time. This practice is indeed beneficial for a new mother who will need mothering herself. With proper care, a mother would also deepen and gain the mental, emotional, and spiritual resources needed to carry her though all the demands of family life, without feeling depleted. [15,16]

Conclusion and Recommendations:

In this study, optimal BPACR practice was found to be 49.31%. Women, who were educated above middle school, had better awareness about various components of BPACR. Hence, repeated awareness programs should be conducted with special emphasis on women with low educational status and their families. Adequate knowledge should be provided to antenatal women about identification of a compatible blood donor and key danger signs. Ambient prenatal care environment goes a long way in fostering sound mental status among antenatal mothers and attempts to explore this should be attempted during home visits and incorporated as a part of micro birth planning. In this way we can tap the existing resources for optimal mental health of the mother and thereby favorable delivery outcomes.

Comprehensive Prenatal Care: Recognizing the impact of social support and stressors, comprehensive prenatal care should encompass more than just physical health examinations. It should also include assessments of the mother's emotional well-being, access to support systems, and interventions to address stress or depression if identified.

Multidisciplinary Approach: Addressing both prenatal support and stressors requires a multidisciplinary approach. This involves collaboration between healthcare providers, mental health profes-

sionals, and community resources to ensure that expecting mothers receive comprehensive care.

Educational and Emotional Support: Prenatal care should not only focus on physical health but also on providing educational resources and emotional support. This can empower mothers with the knowledge and tools needed for a healthy pregnancy and childbirth experience.

Community and Cultural Considerations: Tailoring support systems to the specific needs of diverse communities is crucial. Cultural competence in prenatal care ensures that interventions are effective and respectful of the unique circumstances of different populations.

In summary, acknowledging and addressing the psychosocial aspects of pregnancy, including social support and stressors, is integral to comprehensive prenatal care. This approach contributes to positive maternal health outcomes and fosters a healthier start for the newborn.

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